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Location-enabled IoT (LE-IoT): Indoor Localization for IoT Environments using Machine Learning

1st Tanveer Ahmad

*Department of Computer Science
University of Cyprus)
Nicosia, Cyprus
tahmad01@ucu.ac.cy*

2nd Xue Jun Li

*Dep of Electrical and Electronic Engineering
Auckland University of Technology
Auckland, New Zealand
xuejun.li@aut.ac.nz*

3rd Muhammad Ashfaq

*Department of Electronics Engineering
University of Engineering & Technology
Taxila, Pakistan
muhammad.ashfaq@uettaxila.edu.pk*

4th Michalis Savva

*Department of Computer Science
University of Cyprus &
CYENS Centre of Excellence
Nicosia, Cyprus
savva.michalis@ucy.ac.cy*

5th Iacovos Ioannou

*Department of Computer Science
University of Cyprus &
CYENS Centre of Excellence
Nicosia, Cyprus
ioannou.iakovos@ucy.ac.cy*

6th Vasos Vassiliou

*Department of Computer Science
University of Cyprus &
CYENS Centre of Excellence
Nicosia, Cyprus
vasosv@ucy.ac.cy*

Abstract—In recent years, the concept of the Internet of things (IoT) has become ubiquitous among several applications. However, traditional localization methods face challenges in accurately measuring sensor node positions, particularly in scenarios involving wireless signal instability, energy harvesting, anchor mobility, latency, and dense environmental conditions. However, these problems open the new ways to utilize machine learning (ML) and self-calibration for localization. To defeat these problems, in this paper, we have proposed a new localization technique, which reduces the localization error caused by the iterations in a triangulation method and drastically shortens the computation time for full network coverage despite noisy environments. First, we present a localization technique based on a looped network. The link quality induction (LQI) is used to formulate multiple feature vectors for the localization problem, solved using linear regression. Second, we examine the appropriateness of a few algorithms under different trade-offs by testing the localization accuracy for different network parameters, including the anchor node density, additive noise, and quality of the wireless channel. The simulation achieves exciting results that the adoption of a support vector machine (SVM) and nonlinear regression model applied with a radial basis function (RBF) kernel leads to an enhanced localization error with Root-Mean Square Error (RMSE) of 0.25m. Furthermore, we gain 48.5% accuracy in the localization error by implementing two models.

Index Terms—Regression, Support vector machine (SVM), Machine learning, Localization, Internet of Things (IoT)

I. INTRODUCTION

With the growth of context-aware, pervasive, and human-centric computing, there has been a notable rise in interest in the literature regarding the expansion of intelligent Indoor Positioning Systems (IPS). Furthermore, wireless communication systems often employ different devices, appliances, vehicles and other objects characterized by self-organized networks operating through multi-hop transmission, commonly known as the Internet of Things (IoT). IoT adds different services

which are essential for connected living initiatives. Among those value added services, localization is one of the prominent one. Localization has a great significance in security, disasters, monitoring, and surveillance. The localization and tracking of objects are not a new concepts. Satellite-based object tracking has been employed since the 1960s, with NASA initiating the tracking of US naval ships and submarines during that period [1], which further enhanced in 1970s by US and USSR [2]. The Global positioning system (GPS) was started in 1993. Recently, the IoT based localization and tracking have gain a huge attention due to their ubiquity and accuracy.

Several IoT localization techniques have been proposed so far for both indoor and outdoor environments. However, most of the techniques only focus on the accuracy of localizing a single sensor or mobile node and jamming attack which require positioning mechanism after the detection [3], [4]. Many applications require the location of all the nodes to fully utilize the data obtained from different premises. Due to the wireless communication instability, the range-based localization approaches, which compute the position of all sensor nodes in a network, face numerous challenges in terms of network coverage, positioning accuracy, noisy data, and weak signals. In addition to the above challenges, an IPS may have a certain degree of complexity, high installation costs, and robustness.

A. Motivation

Indoor IoT localization is considered to be the main application for different location based services (LBS), such as the tracking of goods, patient monitoring in hospitals, and customer monitoring in malls. The Global Satellite Navigation Systems (GNSS) is a de facto standard for outdoor scenarios. Although indoor localization has been an active research area, thus far, there is no agreed-upon solution for indoor environments a combination of ML and regression modeling.

Furthermore, it was observed that noisy channels and channel estimation are not considered in most algorithms. To the best of our knowledge, mobile anchor nodes have yet to be deployed in parametric loop algorithms (PLD) [5], where the entire region is divided into several 3D networks. Motivated by this fact, we proposed a novel solution with high precision that handle channel estimation and a noisy distribution of data for the regression data set. We have used an ML-based approach to improve the location performance for indoor environments, with a special focus on low-cost wearable devices.

B. Contributions

The PLD algorithm for IoT localization has only been implemented for static networks along with the use of RSS values. The multiple RSS values in a matrix can create a lot of anomalies and hence it is very hard to implement an ML model for such data. In order to reduce the dataset in a matrix we have adopted the LQI values which not only reduce the data element but are trained easily for self-localization purposes. Hence the proposed technique is novel by adopting the LQIs. The proposed solution also satisfies the following requirements of a localization algorithm.

- 1) The algorithm can easily work on static as well as mobile-based localization systems. Currently, the mobile anchor has not been deployed in PLD technique.
- 2) As none of the node listens to any anchor node, hence connectivity information may be used for localization.
- 3) A dataset should be minimal so that it can be easily trained for the self-localization purpose.

The proposed schemes with the help of a minimal data matrix and ML model can provide fast localization. Our main contribution was to use the LQI values and after that train LQI data using regression and an SVM-based model for self-localization of the nodes. The use of LQI in the proposed technique helps us to solve the localization problem with machine learning models. The machine-learning (ML) models for large-scale localization have been implemented in the proposed work to testify which model is suitable for reducing the error. The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section 2 explains the literature survey. The proposed solution is presented in section 3, whereas the simulation and performance analysis is in section 4, which is followed by a few discussions and concluding remarks in Section 5 and 6.

II. RELATED WORK AND BACKGROUND

Before delving into the literature survey section, we will provide some background information on RSSI and LQI.

A. RSSI vs LQI

LQI and RSSI are two properties of radio signal, which do not require prior information regarding communication protocol and can be obtained by received signal data. For RSS computation no additional hardware is needed and almost every node in the network can analyze the signal strength. The RSS is computed by Equation 1. On the other hand, LQI is an indication of link quality data packets, and can be used

as an estimation of the quality of the signal. In localization, many algorithm has uses the highest values of the RSS as a LQI from the data set. Few of the literature use signal-to-noise ratio (SNR), as a distance estimator, which is another way to judge the signal quality. Given that LQI is a superior metric, it should not be forgotten that it is only made available by 802.15.4 compliant devices through IEEE(mgmt) command.

B. Localization Algorithms

Localization algorithms are categorized into centralized and distributed, range-free and range-based, anchor-based and anchor-free, GPS and non-GPS, and coarse-grained and fine-grained [6]. Along with the estimation techniques AoA, ToA, TDoA, and RSSI. These estimated methods are then merged using trilateration or triangulation for computing the node position. RSSI-based techniques are more popular and are widely used. However, RSSI-based methods are inefficient because of weak signals owing to multipath fading, additive noise, shadowing, and interference. An alternative is to compare the RSSI to a fixed power threshold, which significantly improves the signal measurement. Such techniques assume that all anchor nodes have a known circular transmission radius with decreasing signal power at a long distance. Subsequently, the intersection of the overlapped circular disks is computed using interval analysis, variational filter, particle filter, and polar-interval analysis [7]. Positioning in ad-hoc networks (APS) based on GPS triangulation was presented in [8], in which the nodes know their location in a coordinate system, and AoA is estimated using GPS devices.

Range-based positioning techniques compute the distance using the time of flight (ToF), ToA, TDoA, or RSSI. Ranging methods have low accuracy due to high cost, complexity, and noise. Furthermore, it is not even practical to equip all nodes with ranging capability in a large network. ToA-based methods compute the target nodes' location, receiving the time of arrival packet from the beacon nodes, which is regulated by multiplying the propagation time by the propagation speed of a signal. As an inexpensive approach, the received signal defines a precise model by assuming path loss attenuation among the distances which require low computation and energy [9]. The distance is then obtained using the ToA method where beacon position is as $\langle (x_1, y_1), \dots, (x_N, y_N) \rangle$ and the location of the target node is estimated using $X = [x, y^T]$. Then the coordinate matrix is obtained by $X = (A^T A)^{-1} A^T B$.

TDoA, like ToA, needs signal arrival time, but involves two signals, usually radio, acoustic, or ultrasound. The best approach to TDoA was presented in [10], where an ultrasound pulse and radio signal were directed simultaneously. Similarly, the distance between the receiver and sender is computed by multiplying the speed of the ultrasound signal by the time difference, that is, $dist = ((t_3 - t_2) - (t_1 - t_0)) \left(\frac{v_{RF} v_{US}}{v_{RF} - v_{US}} \right)$. In [11], the localization error was critically analyzed with respect to TDoA for indoor environments, and specific hardware was designed for signal measurements. The overall progress was influenced by a few other components such as the update rates and latency.

TABLE I: Comparison between different indoor localization algorithms

Localization Techniques	Features and Characteristics	Weakness	Usage and Application
AoA	Uses angle information between fixed and a mobile terminal as well as intersection to compute location.	Requires extra hardware (antenna arrays) and causes extra cost for a large node size.	Suitable for fixed terminals because of its larger size. For mobile terminals a huge antenna array is required.
ToA	Uses distance measurement between anchor and sensor nodes	Requires one-way ranging with full synchronization	Suitable for cellular networks
TDoA	Utilizes difference among ToAs of different targeted nodes.	Requires highly accurate synchronization between mobile nodes	Suitable for WSNs
RSSI	Estimates distance based on attenuation through signal propagation from fixed to mobile nodes	Requires precise propagation model for distance computation and expects low precision in localization	Suitable for coarse estimation because of low accuracy
Pattern Matching	Uses Fingerprint data of computed radio signal at several locations	Requires off-line data base update which may not useful on any channel or under environmental change	Suitable for wireless LAN with RSS saved in database. May be used for cellular network.

AoA-based methods adopt an angular estimation instead of a distance estimation. In [12], phase array radar and smart synchronization utilize angle measurements with a high localization error, applying the polarization pattern of the antenna, which is known as "beamforming". Its practical implementation is attained for ALDR in an indoor area of $(10 \times 10)m$ under two beacon nodes. The experimental results exhibited an overall localization accuracy of $124cm$ [13]. Two other schemes, "maximum point minimum rectangle (MPMR)" and "maximum point minimum diameter (MPMD)", also reflects the angle estimation with more beacon nodes and more excellent network coverage [14]. The idea is much similar to that in [13]; however, the use of most likelihood (ML)-based estimation gradually decreases the localization error by up to 29%. Most of the AoA-based techniques are considered to have a noisy distribution, including an adequate complementary variable strategy, that is, $\hat{\beta}_j = \beta_j + \sigma\beta_j$ is used to extract two AoA techniques. Here, β_j is the exact computation of AoA from j th beacons and an additive noise σ satisfies the relation $\sigma\beta_j \approx (c, \sigma_j^2)$.

In any of the localization schemes, the distance among the neighbors is measured by using the RSS or LQI values. Friis' free space transmission equation is used to derive the theoretical properties of RSSI, where the signal quality loss with the large distance to the sender, that is,

$$P_{RS} = P_{TX} G_{RX} G_{TX} \left(\frac{\lambda}{4\pi d} \right)^2, \quad (1)$$

where P_{RX} , P_{TX} is the received power and the transmission power of the sender respectively. In addition, G_{RX} and G_{TX} are the Gain of the receiver and transmitter, respectively. Fingerprinting explains how RSSI is transformed into fingerprints. Fingerprinting consists of an offline phase where the RSS is filled in the central database, and an online phase, where the target nodes inquire about their position from the database [15].

ML techniques can be broadly classified into supervised and unsupervised algorithms. In 2D environment, the sensor nodes compute two coordinates for every target node in real numbers, which lies within a regression problem. The feature data set includes the training phase includes the RSSI measurement whereas the output is two or three variables depending on

whether a 2D or 3D-based system is adopted. A multi-output regression algorithm is preferably implemented because the system has two output variables after converting it to nonlinear optimization. To further discuss an ML-based localization algorithm requiring less computations, [16] proposed a Bayesian algorithm which is an improved version of a progressive correction algorithm [17], both of which use the Cramer-Rao bound (CRB) as a standard. Both algorithms achieve a high precision compared to their predecessors. The relationship between ML-based localization algorithms and other traditional algorithms is presented in Figure 1. A summary of commonly used localization techniques is explained in Table I.

Fig. 1: Classification of localization algorithms in WSNs

III. PROPOSED LOCALIZATION SCHEME

In this section, we discuss the problem statement and the design of the proposed solution under mobility in PLD. The key notations used in the algorithm are described in Table II.

A. System Model

Considering a large-scale IoT based network with N number of nodes $\{K_1, K_2, \dots, K_N\}$ deployed over a 3D region. Each node K_i has communication range $r(K_i)$, which we let the same for all the nodes i.e., $r > 0$. If there is no signal attenuation or blocking, the nodes can communicate with each other within the communication range, hence reachable. We further assume M number of static anchor nodes $\{A_1, A_2, \dots, A_M\}$ and a few of the C mobile anchor nodes $\{S_1, S_2, \dots, S_C\}$ are randomly deployed in a sensing region as shown in Figure 2. The nodes are deployed in layers with different volumes

$\{V_1, V_2, \dots, V_i\}$, which are in sensing region of at least one anchor node.

Fig. 2: System Architecture

TABLE II: Key notations used in the proposed technique

Notation	Explanation
K_1, \dots, K_N	N number of K sensor nodes
A_1, \dots, A_M	M number of A static anchor nodes
S_1, \dots, S_C	C number of S mobile anchor nodes for SVM model
ρ	Center point
μ	Target sensor node
α_i	Exact position of a node
\mathfrak{S}_i	Training dataset extracted from LQI values
$1 \times N$	Extended vector size
\wp	Data for testing in ML model
s	Feature vector
ξ	Absolute Gaussian error
F	Mod function for division
ξ_σ	Noise factor
Λ	Mean error
Γ	Standard deviation

In a proposed technique assuming that only anchor nodes at the boundary can initiate the localization process and compute the node position by forming triangulation. This will help us to train the data matrix for SVM and the regression model. For proper operation, the reference anchor node must select no less than three other anchor nodes for triangulation formulation. Hence, the distance between the nodes is estimated by the Euclidian equation, which is also illustrated in Fig 3.

$$d_{i,j} = |N_1 N_2|^2 = (x_1 - y_1)^2 + (x_2 - y_2)^2 \quad (2)$$

Fig. 3: Euclidean distance among the nodes

B. Algorithm Design

Consider a network model consisting of N target nodes and M mobile anchor nodes with an area under one parametric network. The volume of each network is computed by:

$$Area = \int_a^b g(t)h'(t)dt \quad (3)$$

where $[a, b]$ is the loop interval. It is assumed that all anchor nodes are within the communication range of the other target nodes under triangulation. The first step is to measure the center point. The distance is measured using the n-tuple RSSI values for the initial training phase to describe the feature vectors for the ML algorithm. Therefore, it is practical to define a channel model that creates a feature vector dataset. To transfer the control to the next level we have introduced a threshold mechanism which is also different from the traditional looping method. The threshold is calculated by taking the average of the largest distance from the reference anchor position to all the anchor nodes in a particular network. At each step the LQI is recorded in a matrix. The proposed scheme is easily handled by the ML model because we do not need to compute the center point and threshold value for each network as compared to the traditional looping technique. But at the start of the process, we need to perform the initial computation. To compute the threshold, we can measure the center point of the region. Based on the value of the center point, we can then compute the next circular network. Suppose that a set of mobile anchor nodes with position vector (x, y, z) be $\vec{A} = \vec{A}_1, \vec{A}_2, \dots, \vec{A}_m$, where $m \geq 4$ for proper operation. Considering Figure 4, mobile anchor node \vec{A}_1 is considered a reference node. So, the distance from the target node to the reference anchor node is computed by:

$$A_1 A_{i+1} = \sqrt{(A_{x(i+1)} - A_{x1})^2 + (A_{y(i+1)} - A_{y1})^2 + (A_{z(i+1)} - A_{z1})^2} \quad (4)$$

The distance between \vec{A}_1 and \vec{A}_6 is extremely large; therefore, the mid-point was computed using $\rho = \frac{1}{2}(A_1 A_6)$. The next looped point is computed through a ring matrix followed by the neighboring anchor node, that is,

$$P_{ij} = \frac{3}{8}(\rho + A_i) + \frac{1}{8}(A_{i-1} + A_{i+1}) \quad (5)$$

These looped points help in transferring the reference point to the next network. The distance is measured using the n-tuple RSSI values for the initial training phase to describe the feature vectors for the ML algorithm. Therefore, it is practical to define a channel model that creates a feature vector dataset. Here, $0dBm$, or a value closer to the threshold, will be considered a high-quality RSS. A log-normal shadowing model containing RSS power, which also computes multipath fading, was used for channel modeling.

$$RSS(dBm) = P_{TX} - P_l(d_0) - 10\eta \log_{10} \frac{d}{d_0} + \xi_\sigma \quad (6)$$

where the RSS is in the form of the signal power and d_0 as a reference distance. In addition, ξ_σ is the noise, and η is the path loss exponent. The noise is computed in an additive Gaussian form with zero means and σ as a standard deviation. To generate a training data set (Table III), the LQI, which is the largest value of all the RSS values, is further considered from this point. The LQI will help to generate the training

dataset and automatically reduce the distance matrix. The mobile anchor nodes are assumed to change their location based on mobility, which creates a large dataset in the training phase used by the ML algorithm.

Fig. 4: Illustration of parametric points computation

We define an RSS tuple vector in the form of LQI $LQI[AA]_i$ such that:

$$LQI[AA]_i = \| LQI(A_i, A_1), LQI(A_i, A_2), \dots, LQI(A_i, A_m) \| \quad (7)$$

where $LQI(A_i, A_j)$ is the signal strength measurement from all anchor nodes to the reference node, that is, $1 \leq i, j \leq m$ and $1 \leq P[1, V + 1] \leq m$ in the case of next looping networks. From the reference node in $LQI[AA]_i$ assigned to the maximum LQI, which creates another n-tuple defined during the training phase, we obtain

$$LQI[A\mu]_i = \| LQI(A_i, \mu_1), \dots, LQI(A_i, \mu[N \rightarrow m]) \| \quad (8)$$

where $LQI(A_i, \mu_k)$ is the LQI from target to mobile nodes. The hash vector of the sensor node LQI is recorded, i.e.,

$$LQI[\mu\mu]_i = \| LQI(\mu_i, \mu_1), \dots, LQI(\mu_i, \mu[N \rightarrow m]) \| \quad (9)$$

where $LQI(\mu_i, \mu_j)$ is an RSSI recorded in a data set from the target nodes, and μ_j is the signal power from the sensor nodes to the target nodes. Similarly, the LQI is transmitted from the sensor nodes to the target nodes, i.e.,

$$LQI[\mu A]_i = \| LQI(\mu_i, A_1), LQI(\mu_i, A_2), \dots, LQI(\mu_i, A_m) \| \quad (10)$$

The distance from \vec{A}_1 reference node to other node is:

$$\vec{A}_{i,j} = \arg \max_{\vec{A}_j \in A} | LQI[AA]_i, LQI[A\mu]_i, LQI[\mu\mu]_i, LQI[\mu A]_i | \quad (11)$$

After obtaining these vectors, we can now state the “feature vector” used later in the ML model, for testing in the training phase. In general, we describe two types of feature vectors: feature reduction vectors and feature extended vectors.

- 1) A reduction vector containing data for target or anchor nodes by excluding target node information and retaining only anchor node values, defining training data for mobile anchors in pairs for the ML algorithm.

$$[LQI[AA]_i, \alpha_i] \Rightarrow 1 \leq i \leq k \quad (12)$$

where α_i is the exact position of a node, and $LQI[AA]_i$ is a reduced LQI vector defined in Equation 7.

- 2) Despite excluding LQI from IoT nodes in the reduction vector, it’s essential to include these values for localization. Because target node which is a vital element, require for network coverage. Additionally, LQI transmitted from sensors to mobile nodes (fewer in numbers) is linked to estimated positions. Extending target nodes with l tuples of LQI values against each target node defines the training vector for all anchor nodes.

$$[LQI[\mathfrak{S}_i, \alpha_i] \Rightarrow [[LQI[AA]_i, LQI[A\mu]_i] \quad (13)$$

where $LQI[\mathfrak{S}_i]$ denotes the training phase dataset. The training dataset is now a part of the extended feature vector and must be recorded against each anchor node corresponding to its exact position. The extended vector size is $1 \times N$, where training data are recorded in matrix form, that is, $m \times (N + 1)$

$$LQI[\mathfrak{S}] = (LQI[\mathfrak{S}]_1, \alpha_1), \dots, (LQI[\mathfrak{S}]_m, \alpha_m) \quad (14)$$

The extended vector against the target nodes is expressed by $LQI[\varphi]_j = [LQI[\mu\mu]_i, LQI[\mu A]_i]$, where $LQI[\varphi]_j$ denotes the test data for the second phase. In proposed algorithm, we compare and analyze the results of both SVM and linear regression for all N target nodes. The simulation was conducted for training data obtained from the reduction vector and by including the target node data set in the extended phase. As we want to forecast unremitting localize nodes, regression-based modeling should be adopted on an independent set of data obtained during the training phase.

1) *Regression Models for MSE:* Several models have been implemented for ML-based localization, including NN, SVM, regression, and multiple regression models with liner classifiers or kernels and random and k-nearest clustering. For a large dataset and parametric points, we used multiple regression and SVM models with a radial basis function (RBF) kernel because our network is divided into non-overlapped vectors or clusters. The model we are using in our proposed solution is the multiple regression model which is the simplest technique and is widely used in WSN localization. The slope of the anchor mobility in linear regression is $\nu_\theta(s) = \theta_0 s_0 + \theta_1 s_1 + \dots + \theta_n s_n$ or $\nu_\theta(s) = \theta^T s$ where $\theta = [\theta_0, \dots, \theta_n]$ and $s = [s_0, \dots, s_n]$. The cost function is defined as:

$$\propto (\theta_0, \dots, \theta_n) = \frac{1}{2m} \sum_1^m (\nu_\theta(s^i) - \alpha^i)^2 \quad (15)$$

where s denotes a feature vector. To minimize the cost function, we adopted the Gradient descent versus cost function. We have selected the Gaussian process to underlie the relationship between LQI, s , and sensor points in 2D space, and, position P . This will be denoted by the following spatial process.

$$s_i = f(P) + \xi \quad (16)$$

where $f(P)$ is a point in network space and ξ denotes the noisy Gaussian error. For regression modeling, the obtained LQI values are used in the maximum likelihood estimator (MLE). The position P is taken as constant in MLE, whereas LQI is a random variable. The posterior distribution corresponds to the sensor points in terms of Bayesian optimization.

$$r(f(P) | s, P) = \frac{r(f(P) | s, P)r(f(P))}{r(P | s)} \quad (17)$$

where $r(f(P) | s, P)$ is a likelihood function, which observes the chance of obtaining LQI values, along with the prior distribution $r(f(P))$. For observing LQI values the MLE is denoted by $\Omega(s | P)$, where the likelihood might be a function of P , which can be maximized in the following form for MLE position estimation.

$$\hat{P} = \arg \max_P \lambda(P) \quad (18)$$

where \hat{P} is an estimated position and $\lambda(\cdot)$ is a maximized function of MLE. The matrix from Eq 11, helps to compute the mean against each reference point.

$$RP_r = \begin{bmatrix} LQI[AA]_1 & LQI[AA]_2 & \dots & LQI[AA]_i \\ LQI[A\mu]_1 & LQI[A\mu]_2 & \dots & LQI[A\mu]_i \\ LQI[\mu\mu]_1 & LQI[\mu\mu]_2 & \dots & LQI[\mu\mu]_i \\ LQI[\mu A]_1 & LQI[\mu A]_2 & \dots & LQI[\mu A]_i \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

$$rp_{r, \hat{A}_{i,j}} = F \left(\sum_{i=1}^j rp_{r, \hat{A}_{i,j}}^i \right) \quad (20)$$

Now the noise factor is also added to the distance measurement for all the N number of nodes i.e.,

$$RP = \left\{ rp_{r, \hat{A}_{i,j}, 1}, \dots, rp_{r, \hat{A}_{i,j}, N} \right\} + \xi_\sigma \quad (21)$$

The mean error and standard deviation is:

$$\Lambda = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N r, \hat{A}_{i,j}, i \quad (22)$$

$$\Gamma = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (r, \hat{A}_{i,j}, i - \Lambda)^2} \quad (23)$$

2) *SVM for Mobile Target Localization*: SVM [18], also known as the supervised ML method, is a widely used ML algorithm for classification. After classification, the SVM analyzed the training dataset for a regression and classification analysis. If the training data emphasize nonlinear regression, they are mapped using a nonlinear mapping function. The cost function defined in the regression model for the binary SVM is as follows:

$$|_{min}^\theta \prod_{i=1}^m [\alpha_i \text{cost}_1(\theta^T s^i) + (1 - \alpha_i) \text{cost}_0(\theta^T s^i)] + \frac{1}{2} \prod_{i=1}^n \theta_\alpha^2 \quad (24)$$

which is further simplified using the constraint parameters. In a training segment where the data are linearized, $\theta^T s \geq$

$0 \implies \alpha = 1$ & $\theta^T s < 0 \implies \alpha = 0$. Now, the learner is fully trained using the dataset, thus we can predict the parameters for localization. For instance, we predict $y = 1$ if $\theta_0 + \theta_1 f_1 + \dots + \theta_n f_n \geq 0$ for all training data elements. To gain a high accuracy in localization error prediction, the "Kernel" function in an SVM provides high robustness. The kernel function helps determine an influential feature data-set, for adjusting the SVM model on the training data. Considering the objects from the training data set $(s^1, \alpha^1), (s^2, \alpha^2), \dots, (s^m, \alpha^m)$. Now, we can estimate the original influential feature, that is, $g^i = |g_1^i, g_2^i, \dots, g_m^i|$ for a set of i th data elements. So the feature vectors (originated using the "similarity" function of the SVM) for the estimated position and true target position s^i, α^i are $[g_1^i = |similarity(s^i, V^1)|, g_2^i = |similarity(s^i, V^2)|, \dots, g_m^i = |similarity(s^i, V^m)|]$, where V_m denotes the mobile anchor landmark.

IV. SIMULATION & PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

The proposed algorithm is evaluated in Matlab and XCTU software. The experimental setup consists of 10 anchor nodes and 25 target nodes, randomly deployed within a region of $(1000 \times 1000 \times 1000)m$. All the nodes are IRIS with a Crossbow sensor board MTS310CA, having 16MHz Atmel microprocessor, 51-pin connector, and 2.4GHz ATmel AT86RF230 radio transceiver. The microprocessor has 8kb RAM, 512kB flash memory. Atmel sensor board outfit with a thermistor, microphone, photoresistor (Clairex CL94L), loop detector, and 2-axis magnetometer. Figure 5 shows the experimental setup along with the mid-point, parametric point, and LQI computation in Figure 6.

Fig. 5: Sensor and anchor node deployment

Fig. 6: RSS, midpoint, and parametric point computation

The system achieves an extremely high accuracy owing to the grid, the parametric nature of the anchor node deployment, and the use of the channel model expressed in Equation 6, with a default value of $55mW$ for power transmission, $\eta = 2$ [a value between 2-4 is good for the indoor environment], and an AGN variable having zero mean and $\sigma = 2.4$ as the standard deviation. For a parameterized network, the area is computed under an arc for full network coverage. The values of the explicated parameters are presented in Table III, which are even rehabilitated according to the environment. The number of anchor nodes is varied to verify the authenticity of the localization scheme. For the regression and SVM modeling, Equation 14 with RSS value is fed into the cost function such that the regressor coefficient is independently trained for the three-coordinate system.

TABLE III: Simulation parameters for different ML model

ML Testing	Number of Anchor nodes	Number of Target nodes	P_{TX} (mW)
Modelling with target nodes	60	100-200	55
Modelling with Anchor nodes	40-80	150	55
Transmission power Testing	60	150	30-90
RSS Quality	60	150	55
Communication Radius	50m		
Initial target state vector $\vec{A}_{i,j}$	(15,17,0,0)		
Trans. and receiver antenna gain	1dB		
Path Loss Exponent	2		
RBF Constant	1		

After obtaining the training phase dataset, we can compute the LE using the centroid formula. All distances are taken from the LQI matrix obtained during the training phase. Because no iterations are involved, the test is revised 100 times. For the initial simulation with $A = 10$ and $N = 25$ the overall average LE of $0.25cm$ is recorded. We gradually increase the number of anchor nodes along with corresponding target nodes and the error was reduced in the case of the higher grid of anchor nodes. From Figure 7, it is to be noted that LE decreases with the increase in the number of anchor nodes. For instance, for $A = 10, A = 30$ anchor nodes with a favorable increase in the number of target nodes, the LE remains the same. With $A = 10$ and $N = 50$, the LE dramatically increases after multiple tests. In the initial simulation, we increased the number of anchor nodes while keeping the number of anchor nodes fixed. The LE is accurate because the training data generated by the reduced factors are obtained from the anchor nodes only.

Regression models with extended feature datasets act differently, because the training data set is now full of RSS values, and hence a better training of the ML algorithm. For instance, the LE reduce in the case of multiple regression models with a large multiple-sensor network. However, the LE increase in the case of the SVM regression model indulges with RBF kernel

because of a high number of sensor nodes against anchor nodes as shown in Figure 8a. This is due to an over-fitting of the training dataset, which is incomplete against the high length of the feature vector. From the sensor node density, it was also observed that extended features play a crucial role in the improvement of the LE. We define two defined vectors, i.e., a reduction vector for RSS to cost function and an extended feature vector that is normalized for forming localization into ML technique. We use RBF and kernels for regression and SVM modeling.

Fig. 7: Mean Localization error vs anchor node density

During the second phase, we tested the anchor node density for the reduced and extended feature vectors. It is clear that the LE performance improved when the number of anchor nodes increased, as shown in Figure 8b. Interestingly, both the multiple and SVM models predict better results in the case of extended features because of the large RSS value in the training data set. Simulation shows that the localization error with the SVM model is reduced the by almost 70%. The proposed algorithm is also compared with state-of-the-art localization algorithm with ML implementation. The interesting fact is the LE is reduced only with extended features either its SVM or regression based modelling. In [19], author has proposed a novel technique to overcome LE based on RSSI obtained through blue-tooth (BLE) nodes. After having RSS values the dataset is trained and obtained the extended feature vectors for localization. An overall $1.3cm$ error were recorded because of multiple RSS dataset which is not fully trained in regression and SVM stage. In another method [20], using two-phase smartphone localization with the help of RSS fingerprinting of long term evolution (LTE), wi-fi, internal camera and Bluetooth signal is proposed for indoor environment. The proposed solution is unique as its exploits SVM in whole network for obtaining regression function. However, if there are not enough nodes in a boundary of the network the MSE leads to $2.4cm$. But its further reduced upto $0.9 - 1cm$ by extending the training dataset and features. The comparison is shown in Figure 8c.

Fig. 8: LE computation and comparison analysis along multiple regression and SVM under reduced and extended features with different sensor and anchor node % density

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we proposed a novel localization algorithm based on parametric loop division along with a machine-learning algorithm, that is free from node synchronization and only requires the RSS distance. We studied many regression and classification-based localization models and finally decided to implement regression-based techniques including multiple regression and SVM regression models, which do not require any iterations. By starting with the proposed solution and RSS measurement, we defined a novel feature vector as a reduced and extended feature that helps to generate the training data set in a bulky form. By implementing the multiple regression and SVM models, we noticed that the SVM-based extended feature regression provides a high accuracy even in the noisy distribution of the dataset. The overall performance of the proposed system provides insight into the overall localization error of 0.25cm which is far better than that of the existing localization algorithms.

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